

Use of Telluratoargentate(III), Periodatocuprate(III) and Telluratocuprate(III) as Oxidants in Mixture Analysis: Determination of Oxalic and Succinic Acids: and Formaldehyde, Formic Acid and Methyl Alcohol in Mixtures

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THE present communication describes a method for determining the individual constituents in mixtures of (i) oxalic and succinic acids employing periodatocuprate(III) and telluratocuprate(III) as oxidants and (ii) formaldehyde, formic acid and methyl alcohol employing telluratoargentate(III) and telluratocuprate(III) as oxidants under varying experimental conditions and in microscale. The method developed is highly specific and gives results reproducible within $\pm 1\%$.

Oxalic acid, succinic acid, formaldehyde, formic acid and methyl alcohol required 2, 14, 4, 2 and 6 equivalents of the oxidant respectively per g. mole of the substrate for complete oxidation into carbon dioxide and water, whereas in case of oxidation of formaldehyde to formic acid at room temperature (30°) with telluratoargentate(III), 2 equivalents of oxidants were required. Interference was observed in the presence of oxidizable substances.

Materials and Methods :

Telluratoargentate(III), periodatocuprate(III) and telluratocuprate(III) reagents were prepared and standardised as described earlier.^{1,2,3} Redistilled formaldehyde(BDH) was used and its solution was standardised by hydroxylamine hydrochloride as described by Donnally⁴.

Determination of Oxalic and Succinic Acids in Mixtures :

For determining oxalic acid, an aliquot of the mixture solution containing oxalic and succinic

acids was boiled with an excess of periodatocuprate(III) and the unused periodatocuprate(III) determined by silver nitrate² after cooling. Another aliquot of the mixture solution was boiled for 30 minutes with an excess of telluratocuprate(III) solution and the remaining oxidant estimated by arsenite method³. The amount of telluratocuprate(III) consumed corresponds to the total amount of oxalic and succinic acids in the mixture. Blank experiments were carried out concurrently under identical conditions.

Determination of Formaldehyde, Formic Acid, and Methyl Alcohol in Mixtures.

To determine formaldehyde, an aliquot of the solution mixture containing formaldehyde, formic acid and methyl alcohol was treated with an excess of telluratoargentate(III) for 1 hour at 30° and the unused telluratoargentate(III) determined iodometrically¹. Another aliquot of the solution mixture was treated with telluratoargentate(III) as above and then kept at 80° for 3 hr. The unused telluratoargentate(III) was estimated as usual¹. The amount of the oxidant corresponds to the total amounts of formaldehyde and formic acid in the mixture. A similar aliquot of the solution mixture was refluxed with an excess of telluratocuprate(III) for 1 hr and the unused oxidant determined iodometrically³. The amount of telluratocuprate(III) consumed corresponds to the total amount of formaldehyde, formic acid and methyl alcohol. Blank experiments were carried out under identical conditions. Estimation of individual constituents in the mixtures was made by considering the difference in the consumption and equivalence of the oxidants.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF OXALIC AND SUCCINIC ACIDS IN MIXTURES

Mixture taken	Oxalic Acid (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Succinic Acid (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Periodato- cuprate(III) consumed (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Oxalic Acid found (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Tellurato- argentate (III) consumed (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Succinic Acid found (g. mole $\times 10^3$)
	1.00	4.00	2.00	1.00	7.64	4.03
	2.50	3.00	4.98	2.49	9.15	2.98
	3.65	2.00	7.30	3.65	10.11	2.01
	4.00	1.00	7.94	3.97	10.34	1.00
	5.25	0.59	10.64	5.30	11.43	0.59

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF FORMALDEHYDE, FORMIC ACID AND METHYL ALCOHOL IN MIXTURES

Mixture taken (g. mole $\times 10^3$)			Tellurato- argentate(III) consumed at room temp. (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Formal- dehyde found (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Tellurato- argentate(III) consumed (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Formic acid found (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Tellurato- cuprate(III) consumed (g. mole $\times 10^3$)	Methyl Alcohol consumed (g. mole $\times 10^3$)
Formalde- hyde	Formic Acid	Methyl Alcohol						
2.50	22.50	10.00	5.02	2.51	5.52	22.60	11.58	10.10
5.00	20.00	8.75	10.00	5.00	6.02	20.10	11.24	8.70
10.00	15.00	7.50	20.10	10.05	7.00	14.90	11.51	7.52
15.00	10.00	5.00	30.16	15.08	8.05	10.01	11.07	5.03
20.00	5.00	2.50	40.20	20.10	9.04	5.00	10.55	2.51

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Study of Stepwise Complexation of Fe(III) with 1-hydroxy phthalaz-4-one in DMF

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SOME phthalazones have attracted much attention in recent years not only on account of their structural ambiguity¹⁻³ and chemiluminescent⁴ properties but also due to their antitubercular activity⁵. Some of the phthalazones were found to be more active than the hydrochlorides of streptomycin and dihydrostreptomycin⁶. Still they have not been placed in medicinal use probably on account of their injurious effect on human tissues. However, one may expect that some non-injurious phthalazone complexes may be of vital importance from medicinal point of view. Practically no attempt has been made with an intention to investigate the possibility of the formation of complexes by phthalazones or substituted phthalazones. The work of Drew and Garwood⁷ to investigate the structure of isomeric N-methylated compounds of 5-nitro-1,4-dihydroxy phthalazine, described as α - and β -series, involves the preparation of Cu(II) complexes of substituted phthalazones, in which both, the phthalazone ring and the substituent occupy the coordination site simultaneously. Therefore, the aim of the present work is to investigate the possibility of formation of complexes by phthalazone with Fe(III), which may be of immense interest to the biochemists and further, to evaluate the thermodynamic properties such as stability constant and the free energy change in the complexation process.

Experimental

Preparation of 1-hydroxy phthalaz-4-one :

The above compound was prepared from phthalic anhydride, hydrazine sulphate and sodium acetate in dilute acetic acid according to the method described by Drew and Hatt⁸. The crude phthalazone recovered as a precipitate by bubbling carbon dioxide in the reaction mixture was crystallised from DMF and was dried in vacuum desiccator. The compound melted at 341-344°.

Preparation of 0.1M Ferric Chloride Solution in DMF :

Ferric chloride (E. Merck quality) was dried in a desiccator containing conc. H₂SO₄ for two weeks and was dissolved in freshly distilled DMF to have a solution of approximately 0.1M. Its strength was accurately determined by volumetric method⁹.

Spectrophotometric Study

Mole Ratio Method¹⁰ :

A series of solutions were prepared by mixing a definite volume of 0.01M ferric chloride solution with varying amounts of 0.01M phthalazone solution in freshly distilled DMF and diluting them with the solvent to a constant volume. The development of colour was studied at 25° by measuring the optical density at regular intervals. The constancy in the absorbance at a particular wave length was observed some time after three days or more. Therefore the absorbance measurements were made well after a week at 530 nm on a Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 colourimeter using 1 cm effective path. Mean of the absorbances of three specimen of solutions with same metal ligand composition prepared separately was recorded in each case. A graph was obtained by plotting absorbance against the total ligand concentrations (Fig. 1). The absorbances of the

Fig. 1.

ferric chloride solutions of varying concentrations in DMF were also measured and molar absorption coefficient was determined.

The interaction between the solution of Fe(III) ion and phthalazone in DMF was also investigated by Job's method¹¹ of continuous variation.

Results and Discussion

Although a number of methods are available for the calculation of stability constants of complexes with N (total number of complexes) = 2 from spectrophotometric data, the calculation becomes difficult when N is more than 2 and the variation of absorbance as a function of total ligand concentration is monotonic. However extrapolation procedure of Yatsimirskii¹² has been applied in special cases by other workers^{1,3,14}. Newman and Hume¹⁵ have